

README

Trends in Tropical Rainforest Habitat Amount and Fragmentation (1990–2023)

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All data used for this paper was extracted using *Google Earth Engine* and processed using R (version 2025.09.2+418). All products (data cubes) and raw csv files are available at *Zenodo* platform. Each variable is available for the entire study period (1990 to 2023) as a gridded product of 0.4° x 0.4° (.tif rasters ; stacked as *NetCDF* ; .nc).

I. Glossary

The file '*data.csv*' contains grid-cell metrics derived from Google Earth Engine at 0.4° × 0.4° resolution, including TMF land-cover classes (undisturbed, degraded, regrowing, deforested, water, other), forest edge areas computed from non-forest using buffer distances of 100 m, 200 m, 300 m, and 1000 m, and the Global Ecological Zones rainforest mask, covering the period 1990–2023.

<i>Column</i>	<i>Description</i>
<i>index</i>	Unique grid cell identifier.
<i>xmin, xmax, ymin, ymax</i>	Grid cell spatial extent (degrees, EPSG:4326).
<i>TMF</i>	Tropical Moist Forest region: "America", "Africa", or "Asia".
<i>totalHA_UF_m2_year</i>	Area of undisturbed forest (TMF class 1, m ²) per year.
<i>totalHA_Dg_m2_year</i>	Area of degraded forest (TMF class 2, m ²) per year.
<i>totalHA_Rg_m2_year</i>	Area of regenerating forest (TMF class 3, m ²) per year.
<i>total_Def_m2_year</i>	Area of deforested pixels (TMF class 4, m ²) per year.
<i>total_Water_m2_year</i>	Area of water (TMF class 5, m ²) per year.
<i>total_Other_m2_year</i>	Area of other land cover (TMF class 6, m ²) per year.
"gez_tr_rainforest"	Tropical rainforest mask from Global Ecological Zones (1 = rainforest, 0 = other).
<i>EdgeArea_FC1_NF1_m2_year_buffer</i>	Forest edge area (m ²) for FC1 (undisturbed forest) at multiple buffer distances (<100 m, <200 m, <300 m, <1000 m) from non-forest (degraded, deforested, regrowth).

II. Google Earth Engine scripts used for data extraction

- Part 0 : Extracting TMF category coverage per continent
<https://code.earthengine.google.com/ff4cb0116745356861825759260d486e>
- Part 1 : Extracting Habitat Amount data
<https://code.earthengine.google.com/ef3ea782568b2cc700ac39024776c1fa>
- Part 2 : Extracting Edge forest data

<https://code.earthengine.google.com/270ee27617918116d2a171daf11641ea>

- Part 3 : Extracting pixels from the Global Ecological Zones classification (FAO) ‘Tropical Rainforest’ category
<https://code.earthengine.google.com/7d05c98e4a1f7d6c8999bf6803e6d7bd>.

III. Scripts included in the distribution

The following scripts are provided to compute, process, and visualise TMF-derived metrics from Google Earth Engine outputs. Each script has a specific role, from full end-to-end analysis to user-focused exploration of pre-computed data cubes.

<i>Script name</i>	<i>Input(s)</i>	<i>Output function</i>
MainScript.R	<code>data.csv</code> (merged GEE-exported grid-cell data with TMF land-cover classes, edge areas, and GEZ mask)	Computes habitat amount per grid cell and year (1990–2023); computes net forest change (ΔFC); generates regional and global habitat trends; maps habitat suitability (>40%); calculates ΔHA ; ECDF and statistical tests (1990 vs 2023); edge forest analyses for multiple buffer distances; generates plots and summary statistics. Full end-to-end analysis for research purposes; produces figures, metrics, and statistics for publication.
ScriptSupp.R	<code>data.csv</code> (merged GEE-exported grid-cell data)	Computes metrics for habitat amount and forest fragmentation; produces gridded spatio-temporal products: GeoTIFFs and NetCDF cubes; prepares data for external use or further analyses. Focused on generating global data products, cubes, and maps; runs in ~5 min.

ScriptUser.R	NetCDF cubes (from ScriptSupp.R) containing TMF land-cover, forest edges, habitat amount, and validity masks	Visualises global and regional habitat maps; extracts regional statistics (mean HA, edge %); converts units (m ² → km ²); computes ΔHA between years; computes core habitat (interior forest); generates binary maps based on habitat thresholds; ECDF and probabilistic analyses. Designed for users to interactively explore and analyse pre-computed data cubes without re-processing raw CSVs.
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IV. List of produced data cubes

The following NetCDF and raster products were generated from the GEE-derived grid-cell data. They include TMF land-cover categories, habitat amount, forest edge areas, and validity masks for the period 1990–2023, at 0.4° × 0.4° resolution. **All the datacubes and .tif files can be generated using R (ScriptSupp.R → OBJECTIVE 2 — GENERATION OF SPATIO-TEMPORAL DATA CUBES).**

TMF Category Cubes (Cubes 1–6)

- Represent each tropical moist forest (TMF) category from 1990–2023.
- Units: m² per grid cell.
 - Cube01 → Undisturbed forest
 - Cube02 → Degraded forest
 - Cube03 → Deforested areas
 - Cube04 → Regrowth forest
 - Cube05 → Water pixels
 - Cube06 → Other land-cover pixels

Habitat Amount Cubes (Cubes 7–8)

- Represent habitat amount per grid cell (1990–2023).
- Units: % of total grid cell area.
 - Cube07 → Forest cover 1 (undisturbed forest)
 - Cube08 → Forest cover 2 (undisturbed + degraded forest)

Edge Area Cubes (Cubes 9–12)

- Represent forest **edge area** below thresholds (100 m, 200 m, 300 m, 1000 m) for undisturbed forests (1990–2023).
- Units: m² per grid cell.

Masks (Masks 1–3)

- Values: TRUE/FALSE (or 1/NA) to indicate valid areas.
- Mask1 → Tropical rainforest zones (FAO GEZ).
- Mask2 → Valid observations for undisturbed forests (Case A).
- Mask3 → Valid observations for undisturbed + degraded forests (Case B).

<i>File name</i>	Content
Cube01_TMF1_UndisturbedForest_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of undisturbed tropical moist forest (TMF category 1) for all years 1990–2023. Units: m ² per grid cell.
Cube02_TMF2_DegradedForest_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of degraded forests (TMF category 2) for all years 1990–2023. Units: m ² per grid cell.
Cube03_TMF3_DeforestedForest_1990-2023.n	NetCDF cube of deforested areas (TMF category 3) for all years 1990–2023. Units: m ² per grid cell.

c	
Cube04_TMF4_RegrowthForest_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of regrowth forests (TMF category 4) for all years 1990–2023. Units: m ² per grid cell.
Cube05_TMF5_WaterPixels_1990-2023.n	NetCDF cube of water pixels (TMF category 5) for all years 1990–2023. Units: m ² per grid cell.
Cube06_TMF6_OtherLandCoverPixels_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of other land-cover pixels (TMF category 6) for all years 1990–2023. Units: m ² per grid cell.
Cube07_UndisturbedRainforest_HabitatAmount_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of habitat amount per grid cell for forest cover 1 (undisturbed forest). Units: % of total grid cell area.
Cube08_UndisturbedAndDegradedRainforest_HabitatAmount_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of habitat amount per grid cell for forest cover 2 (undisturbed + degraded forest). Units: % of total grid cell area.
Cube09_EdgeArea0100m_m2_UndisturbedRainforest_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of edge forest area < 100 m for undisturbed forests. Units: m ² per grid cell.

Cube10_EdgeArea0200m_m2_UndisturbedRainforest_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of edge forest area < 200 m for undisturbed forests. Units: m ² per grid cell.
Cube11_EdgeArea0300m_m2_UndisturbedRainforest_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of edge forest area < 300 m for undisturbed forests. Units: m ² per grid cell.
Cube12_EdgeArea1000m_m2_UndisturbedRainforest_1990-2023.nc	NetCDF cube of edge forest area < 1000 m for undisturbed forests. Units: m ² per grid cell.
Mask1_GlobalEcologicalZones_TropicalRainforest_FAO_2010.tif	Raster mask for tropical rainforest zones (FAO GEZ). Value = 1 in rainforest, NA elsewhere.
Mask2_ValidObservations_UndisturbedRainforest.tif	Raster mask for valid observations of undisturbed forest (Case A). TRUE where data exists, FALSE/NA otherwise.
Mask3_ValidObservations_UndisturbedAndDegradedRainforest.tif	Raster mask for valid observations of undisturbed + degraded forest (Case B). TRUE where data exists, FALSE/NA otherwise.

V. Instructions for using helper functions on data cubes

This section provides example R scripts for loading, visualising, and analysing the pre-computed NetCDF and raster data cubes. The workflow relies on the R packages **dplyr**, **ggplot2**, and **terra**.

A. Open a and visualize a data cube in R

```
R Script

# Declare entire time series (1990 - 2023)
seq=1990:2023

# Global map : Choose a focal year
focal_year=1997

# Example : Plot map for habitat amount
rcdf=rast("Cube_1_1990-2023_CaseA_UndisturbedRainforest_HabitatAmount
.nc")
nb=which(seq==focal_year)
plot(rcdf[[nb]])

# Example 1 : Compute habitat amount for a subregion, inset defined inset as SpatExtent
ext_AM <- ext(inset_AM$xmin, inset_AM$xmax, inset_AM$ymin,
inset_AM$ymax)

# Select focal year
nb <- which(seq == focal_year)

# Crop habitat amount raster
hab_AM <- crop(rcdf[[nb]], ext_AM)

# Compute mean habitat amount (%)
mean_hab_AM <- global(hab_AM, fun = "mean", na.rm = TRUE)[1,1]

# Print value
cat("Mean habitat amount (%) in inset AM:", round(mean_hab_AM, 2),
"\n")

# Example : Visualize inset for South-America
plot(hab_AM, main = paste("Habitat amount (%) - AM inset -",
focal_year))
```

B. Convert data cube units in R

```
R Script

# Example : Plot map for edge forests < 100m
rcdf=rast("Cube_2_1990-2023_CaseA_UndisturbedRainforest_EdgeArea0100m
```

```
_m2.nc")
```

Convert m² to km²

```
rcdf_km2 <- rcdf / 1e6
```

Example : Plot focal year

```
nb <- which(seq == focal_year)  
plot(rcdf_km2[[nb]], main = paste("Edge forest area (km2) -",  
focal_year))
```

C. Derive habitat amount >40% from habitat amount function and a threshold

R Script

Get forest cover (Undisturbed) and non-forest (the rest)

```
rcdf_FC1=rast("Cube_0_1990-2023_TMF1_UndisturbedForest_.nc")  
rcdf_NF1=rast("Cube_0_1990-2023_TMF2_DegradedForest_.nc")  
rcdf_NF2=rast("Cube_0_1990-2023_TMF3_DeforestedForest_.nc")  
rcdf_NF3=rast("Cube_0_1990-2023_TMF4_RegrowthForest_.nc")  
rcdf_NF4=rast("Cube_0_1990-2023_TMF6_OtherLandCoverPixels_.nc")
```

Get forest cover variable

```
rcdf_FC <- rcdf_FC1
```

Non-forest = sum of all other classes

```
rcdf_NF <- rcdf_NF1 + rcdf_NF2 + rcdf_NF3 + rcdf_NF4
```

Habitat amount (%) = FC / (FC + NF) * 100

```
rcdf_hab <- (rcdf_FC * 100) / (rcdf_FC + rcdf_NF)
```

Mask invalid pixels

```
rcdf_hab <- ifel((rcdf_FC + rcdf_NF) == 0, NA, rcdf_hab)
```

Plot focal year

```
nb <- which(seq == focal_year)  
plot(rcdf_hab[[nb]], main = paste("Habitat amount (%) -",  
focal_year))
```

Example : Pass a minimum habitat amount threshold (Example : 40%)

```
HabAmountThreshold <- 40  
rcdf_hab_bin <- rcdf_hab > HabAmountThreshold  
plot(rcdf_hab_bin[[nb]], col = c("grey90", "darkgreen"))
```

D. Derive habitat amount delta (%) between two years

R Script

Define years

```
year1 <- 1990  
year2 <- 2023
```

Declare layer indices

```
i1 <- which(seq == year1)  
i2 <- which(seq == year2)
```

```

# Compute Habitat Amount delta HA (%) : difference in habitat amount between two years
rcdf_delta_HA <- rcdf_hab[[i2]] - rcdf_hab[[i1]]

# Example : plot Habitat Amount delta HA (%) : difference in habitat amount between two years
plot(rcdf_delta_HA, main = paste("Δ Habitat Amount (%)", year1, year2))

```

E. Derive edge area (%) from edge forest (m2) and non-forest (m2)

R Script

```

# Get forest cover (Undisturbed)
rcdf_FC1 <- rast("Cube1_TMF1_UndisturbedForest_1990-2023.nc")

# Edge forests < 100 m
rcdf_EA <-
rast("Cube9_CaseA_EdgeArea100m_m2_UndisturbedRainforest_1990-2023.nc")

# Compute edge area percentage (%) = (EA / FC) * 100
rcdf_edge <- (rcdf_EA * 100) / rcdf_FC1

# Mask invalid pixels
rcdf_edge <- ifel(rcdf_FC1 <= 0 | rcdf_EA <= 0, NA, rcdf_edge)

# Example: Plot edge area (%) for a focal year
nb <- which(seq == focal_year)
plot(rcdf_edge[[nb]], main = paste("Edge area (%) -", focal_year))

# Example : Compute edge forest area for a subregion (AM inset)
# Crop edge-area-percentage raster to AM inset
edge_AM <- crop(rcdf_edge[[nb]], ext_AM)

# Mean edge forest area (%)
mean_edge_AM <- global(edge_AM, fun = "mean", na.rm = TRUE)[1,1]

```